

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

USE OF PHYSIOLOGICAL, MICROBIOLOGICAL, BIOCHEMICAL, BIOPHYSICAL, TOXICOLOGICAL METHODS IN ASSESSING THE FUNCTIONAL ROLE OF HYDROBIONTS

Zarovshan Babayeva Yashar

prof/doctor of pedagogical sciences

Nakhchivan State University, Azerbaijan

<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-3004-8455>

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Watersheds are polluted mainly due to the release of industrial, agricultural and household waste into watersheds. Pollutants, as well as harmful factors from the atmosphere and as a result of human activities in the basins (shipping, transportation of oil and other products, underwater drilling, logging, etc.) enter the water basins. All this disturbs the ecological balance in the basins, and thus the cleaning process either does not proceed at all or proceeds very slowly. Environmental effects of pollutants in watersheds occur at the organism, population, biocenotic and ecosystem levels. For this reason, the use of physiological, microbiological, biochemical, biophysical, and toxicological methods is important in evaluating the functional role of hydrobionts. At the level of the organism, the physiological functions of living beings are disturbed, changes in their behavior occur, growth slows down, endurance decreases, mortality increases and accelerates. At the population level, pollution affects the number dynamics, biomass, reproductive intensity, density, distribution and size of organisms. At the biocenotic level, pollution manifests itself in the structure and functions of living things as a whole. For example, flagellates are more resistant to oil pollution than diatoms. Therefore, they drastically change the structural structure of the species composition of microplankton. As a result of the influence of pollutants and toxic substances, the structural structure of living things changes, which ultimately leads to the degradation of the ecosystem.

It should be noted that each toxic substance has a specific mechanism of action. Therefore, hydrobionts, their populations and hydrobiocenoses have different sensitivity and resistance to toxicants. Many hydrobionts have evolved the ability to accumulate toxicants in their bodies. Examples of these are radiolarians, jellyfish, molluscs and seaweed. They accumulate toxic substances in their bodies and are considered toxic to other organisms. Aquatic ecosystems are polluted by natural and man-made pollutants. The strongest natural pollutant is considered to be the "blooming" of water bodies. During the strong flowering of the basin, the physical and chemical properties of the water in the basin are changed, and even cases of drowning of living beings are observed. The natural collection of organic substances in water bodies is not a positively vital event for the water basin. In water bodies, plant and animal organisms or their parts fall to the bottom of the water. This process is more intensive in water bodies rich in plants. The organic matter at the bottom of the basin creates

favorable conditions for the strong development of bacteria there. This eventually leads to bacterial contamination of the basin. On the other hand, a large amount of oxygen is absorbed as a result of biochemical processes. On the one hand, the absorption of oxygen, and on the other hand, the decomposition of dead organisms, the accumulation of toxic substances (NH₃, CO₂, H₂S, etc.) in the environment, gradually lowers the quality of water, affects its chemical properties and causes repeated water pollution.

Since natural pollutants, as mentioned above, are directly under the control of nature, such natural-biological processes are created in the basins themselves against such pollution, as a result of which the general physico-chemical properties of the water in the basin remain stable. On the other hand, natural pollutants are the wastes directly caused by a certain part of the products created by nature (pollen, leaf litter and flower petals, etc.) and have a temporary nature. Man-made pollutants As a result of human activity, a large amount of various gas, liquid, colloidal, emulsion and solid pollutants enters the biosphere. Toxic substances released into the atmosphere in gaseous form return to the soil and water bodies through atmospheric sediments. The result of water pollution with one or another toxic substance causes great consequences. Pollutants are usually divided into several groups: household pollutants (waste); industrial pollutants; toxic chemicals and fertilizers; surfactants; radioactive substances and thermal pollutants.

Domestic pollutants were considered as the main pollutant of water bodies until recently. It includes household waste of the population, sewage and waste from livestock farms. The composition of such pollutants mainly consists of various organic substances dissolved in water and in the form of suspended particles. The amount of organic substances in them (58%) is higher than the amount of mineral substances (42%). Household pollutants, unlike industrial pollutants, contain large amounts of disease-causing bacteria and various helminth eggs. There are also microorganisms that can live in such sewage for months. Therefore, household waste water is considered the most dangerous pollutant of basins. The amount of bacteria in each liter of them reaches 400 mg. Such waters radically change the physico-chemical composition of water in the basin. Water becomes cloudy, its taste quality changes, it smells bad, etc. Hydrogen sulfide, methane, ammonia, etc. are released in the basin as a result of decomposition of protein-containing substances collected at the bottom of water

basins. toxic substances are formed. Thus, a repeated source of pollution is generated in the basins. Domestic sewage strongly affects the oxygen regime of the basin.

All this worsens the living conditions of fish and other aquatic organisms and even causes their mass destruction. Such waters can only be used after biological treatment or released into water bodies. Using household waste in agriculture, especially in farming (irrigation) can give better results. Industrial pollutants are considered the main polluters of water bodies in modern times. It includes organic and mineral wastes of various industries, raw materials and reagent residues used in technological processes. The composition of industrial waste is very diverse, and the volume of its discharge into basins is increasing every year. Most of the wastewater enters the basins from chemical, oil, petrochemical, pulp and paper industry enterprises, organic synthesis farms, mining, metallurgical and mine works. In connection with the creation of new industrial areas, new wastewaters of unknown composition and sphere of influence are constantly discharged into basins. Water basins oil and oil products. Research conducted in laboratories is methodologically based on modern approaches to the study of the state of animal populations. Taking into account the results of the laboratory, it allows to carry out the following complex works on the study of water bodies and coastal areas in ecologically unfavorable areas. These cover various areas such as:

- Hydrochemical analysis of water samples: mineral and biogenic composition, assessment of water sample quality and contamination of water bodies with organic and other toxic substances;

- Hydrobiological studies of zooplankton (rotifers, lower crustaceans) and zoobenthos in water bodies and streams; analysis of faunal complexes and species populations according to their structural-functional and informative characteristics; assessment of water quality according to hydrobiological indicators;

- Population genetic studies of diptera (Diptera Nematocerca) and fish; identification of adaptive changes in characteristic chironomid and grenade species in natural and anthropogenic populations;

- Using bioecological and histobiochemical analysis, ichthyological study of the population structure and variability of fish in water bodies with the assessment of the negative impact on fish due to the level of disruption of individual development homeostasis and the presence of histopathological disorders;

- Study of amphibians from the genus *Rana* and evaluation of surveyed populations according to morphological and biochemical indicators and fluctuating asymmetry of bilateral signs;

- Study of small mammal populations (rodents, mice, hamsters) with a number of indicators, including morphometric, morphophysiological, hematological, histological and cytogenetic tests for toxicity to animals and humans;

- Determination and analysis of accumulation levels of pollutants (heavy metals, etc.) in environmental components and indicator animal species in research objects;

- Forming a collection of data for environmental assessment works, etc.

It was determined by A.H. Gasimov that if there are 20-30 mg of oil products in each liter of water, it disrupts the conditional reflex activity of fish, and if it exceeds 30 mg, they die in mass. For chironomid larvae, solar oil is considered more toxic. As a result of the experiments, it was found that if there is 0.4-0.8 mg/l of oil in the environment, the development of swimming crabs living in the Caspian Sea slows down and their productivity decreases. According to the information provided by Z. Rzayev, oil products in the environment at 0.1-0.5 mg/l have a toxic effect on the spermatozoa of bream, sturgeon and longnose fish. So, oil has a great toxic power. Therefore, all processing of oil should be carried out in a closed circuit, and we should try not to let even a drop of it enter our basins. The production of toxic chemicals and fertilizers is expanding every year. These substances are widely used in forestry, agriculture and other fields. It includes various herbicides, insecticides and algicides. According to the latest data, 1.2 mln. tons of pesticides are produced. The amount of artificial fertilizers obtained by chemical means is constantly increasing. If fertilizers are not used properly, it causes unpleasant consequences. There is already information in the scientific literature about the poisoning of people and animals from water contaminated with nitrogenous fertilizers. Toxic chemicals and fertilizers are washed from fields and discharged into water bodies (rivers, lakes and streams) through drainage and main canals. This can lead to the creation of unnatural conditions in water bodies, the destruction of hydrobionts and, in general, the poisoning and complete "death" of the basin. Therefore, when using toxic substances and fertilizers, one should be very careful, they should be used purposefully, and they should be kept far away from areas with water bodies. The production of surfactants and detergents produced from them, which are widely used in industry and household, is also constantly increasing. As soon as surfactants enter the water, they weaken the tension of the water's surface tension membrane and increase its detergency. These substances foam very much in water and are toxic. There are types of washing powders that, when their amount exceeds 0.1 mg per liter of water, all hydrobionts, from invertebrates to fish, perish. However, in addition, there are surfactants that have weak toxic properties. They do not affect water fleas (*Daphnia*) when their amount is up to 5 mg per liter of water. However, it is impossible to keep living things in this solution for a long time (2-3 months). The time of decomposition of surfactants in the water environment is up to 2 months. This fact allows us to say that the organisms in the basins are gradually poisoned and destroyed. Because such substances belong to detergents that cause persistent pollution. Therefore, cod surfactants with strong toxic properties should not be allowed to enter water bodies. Soft surfactants can be released into the basin after full biological treatment (and sometimes additional treatment is required). Radioactive pollutants are created as a result of the use of atomic energy in one or

another field of economy and science. At this time, a large amount of radioactive waste is produced. Sometimes such wastes fall into the environment. When it falls into water bodies, it has a lethal effect on its flora and fauna. As a result of radioactivity, protein synthesis in living beings and also the hereditary characteristics of organisms are disturbed. Radioactive waste can travel through the food chain from single-celled organisms to humans. Hydrobionts (plants and animals) have the ability to absorb radioactive substances from the environment in their organs and tissues. Thus, uranium, radium, zirconium, strontium, plutonium in animal bones; While lanthanum, thorium, and actinium accumulate in the liver, tellurium, tin, antimony, niobium, and others are spread evenly throughout the body. Radioactive substances accumulate more quickly in primitive aquatic organisms. These organisms play the role of transmitters of radioactive substances by forming the food of fish and finally of man. Thermal pollutants are among the pollutants of recent years.

It is known that a large amount of cold water is taken from water basins to cool the units of thermal and nuclear power plants and is returned to the water basin after cooling the engines. The temperature of the water returning to the water basin through the aggregates is higher than the general average temperature of the water in the basin. This ultimately affects the salinity, gas regime and biological composition of the basin water. Recent studies have shown that the release of warm water into basins of fishery importance alters the hydrothermal and biological regime of the basin. The heating of the water mass in the basin due to the hot water entering it (up to 100C) leads to the observation of important disturbances in the biological regime of the basin. First of all, cold-loving - stenothermic forms are gradually decreasing. A "blooming" occurs in the basin, the species composition of zooplankton and benthos decreases. Under such conditions, the feeding intensity of the fish is weakened, the growth of the baby fish is delayed, and the species composition of the fish gradu-

ally changes in favor of the less important fish. In addition to these, conditions are created for fish to develop a number of diseases and be infected with various parasites. Thus, it is clear that we are faced with the need to revise and improve the mechanism of the effect of the use of physiological, microbiological, biochemical, biophysical, toxicological methods and modern technologies on the biology of aquatic organisms in the assessment of the functional role of hydrobionts. Especially in the modern era we live in, the disturbance of the ecological balance for various reasons affects the water bodies, and therefore the development and reproduction of hydrobionts, etc. poses a serious threat.

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